

NFDI4Earth

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Criteria for evaluating the support quality of the OneStop4All

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Executive summary

The OneStop4All (OS4A) is the main access point to all NFDI4Earth resources, and its usability and the quality of the presented content is paramount to the success of the NFDI4Earth. Evaluation of the support quality of the OS4A can be categorised into the usability of the portal website, the subsequent content quality, and the accessible range of topics, and finally the support of the users.

In this first version of the deliverable we describe the preliminary work within the NFDI4Earth expert group "User", the derived criteria, common evaluation schemes and the evaluation methods themselves. We recognise that both the OS4A and the evaluation criteria will need to evolve in tandem, based on the feedback we receive from the community once the OS4A is live.

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1. Introduction

The OneStop4All (OS4A) is the main access point to all NFDI4Earth resources and aims to support all searches and questions that the users from the Earth System Sciences (ESS) might have, e.g., about general principles of FAIR data and data management, about finding and accessing datasets, tools and services and information about the NFDI4Earth organisation and participants.

The OS4A is directly connected to the KnowledgeHub, which holds the metadata of all resources. This ensures that all content can be found by the user via the OS4A. For example, the user can find repositories and archives, articles and teaching materials on various topics of data management, data science and topics related to the NFDI4Earth. The portal offers the possibility of finding the content via a search bar, via lists of the various resource types or also via linked content in the form of e.g. knowledge graphs. For inexperienced users, there are also topic-related entry points, for example, the data search or data publication, and here the corresponding content can be displayed in a focused manner. Furthermore, there is direct access to a learning management system in which users have the possibility to complete courses on various topics in self-study and at their own pace and to monitor their learning progress. The OS4A thus offers many possibilities for finding content and answering users' questions directly.

The OS4A is closely interrelated with the User Support Network (USN, M2.2). Any queries that cannot be answered directly by the OS4A – or for which the user desires human support – are assigned to a category by the users (dropdown, category selection is specified by the USN) and answered by the respective USN members. Hence, evaluating the support quality of the OS4A will happen on various levels, one of which will be analysing the requests to the USN.

In this document we summarise the current evaluation criteria for the overall OS4A support quality, describe the starting point of their development – a collaborative effort within the NFDI4Earth "User"¹ – and delineate transitions to possible other product evaluation mechanisms.

2. Development of evaluation criteria

The initial basis for the evaluation criteria for the OS4A was developed collaboratively during the last meeting of the user expert group in autumn 2022, a brainstorming session, where evaluation criteria for a wide range of NFDI4Earth products (OS4A, USN, LivingHandbook

¹ At the beginning of the project, NFDI4Earth members formed so-called expert groups. Each group had a specific topic on which they worked together. The NFDI4Earth expert group "Users" included members from all NFDI4Earth components and focused on the different target groups of the NFDI4Earth products.

(LHB), KnowledgeHub (KH), EduTrain, Academy and the NFDI4Earth in general) were collected (see Appendix sec. A). The creation of the criteria and methods was based on already proven approaches from Nielsen (1992), Jacobsen (2017) and Norman (2013).

As the OS4A will be the central entry point to access the NFDI4Earth resources, many of the quality criteria for other products will therefore be experienced by the users via the OS4A and are related to measures of content quality (e.g., for KH and LHB content). However, some of the ideas from the initial collection refer to internal feedback of the KH and the LHB, e.g., via the portal for direct interaction with the KH or the feedback mechanisms of the editorial board of the LHB. These points will be discussed in specific documents of the respective products and hence omitted here.

The EduTrain and Academy evaluation will also not be discussed further in this document. The EduTrain will have a separate learning management system (LMS). Feedback and quality evaluation will be discussed separately in the respective measure. The Academy is also not directly accessed via the OS4A. The support quality which can be tracked via the USN requests, however, directly relates to the OS4A and is part of this overview.

Evaluation of the OS4A support quality combines various aspects: (1) usability of the portal website, (2) the content quality and range of topics, which should help to answer the targeted users' research questions and (3) the support of the users, which touches both the use of the website and the connection to the USN.

There are different schemes which help to assess support quality (e.g. <https://www.userlike.com/de/blog/grundsaeetze-guter-kundenservice>) or user experience for web applications (e.g. <http://static.googleusercontent.com/media/research.google.com/de//pubs/archive/36299.pdf> and usability (e.g. <https://www.usability.gov/what-and-why/usability-evaluation.html>)

We merge the most relevant of the suggestions of these schemes and refine and categorise the initially collected brainstorming ideas in the following section.

3. Evaluation criteria for support quality of the OneStop4All

The evaluation methods and criteria in this overview mainly refer to the project phase, in order to iteratively improve the support quality of the OS4A via regular feedback loops and adaptations. The criteria will be extended and revised over time and will differ in a productive system after the project ends. Criteria for content quality will also very much evolve with user feedback.

- (1) Criteria for the usability of the portal website (Nielsen, 1992 and Norman, 2013)
 - a. Intuitive design and effortless understanding of architecture and navigation (e.g., how often are search processes adjusted?)

- b. Ease of learning: how fast can a new user accomplish basic tasks?
- c. Efficiency of use: how fast can an experienced user accomplish tasks? (e.g., how much time does it take to find the desired data/information?)
- d. Memorability: can a user remember enough to use the site effectively in future visits
- e. Error frequency and severity during use and how fast users recover from them

(2) Criteria for content quality and range of topics

- a. LHB content:
 - i. number of references from outside
 - ii. flagging “outdated”/“error”
 - iii. feedback of issues and update request via feedback form
 - iv. rating of articles
- b. KH content:
 - i. datasets are FAIR
 - ii. datasets answer to to community standards and recommendations
 - iii. full and understandable (meta)data
 - iv. Number of interconnected resources as a step towards interoperability.

(3) Criteria for user support, in terms of website usage and content quality of the OS4A as well as the connection to the USN

- a. Speed: Fast service means convenience for the user. Speed is a decisive factor for user satisfaction
- b. Accuracy: Result of OS4A search/USN response needs to be primarily correct, i.e. answer the user’s question. This refers to good and dependable search functionality, which is possibly more relevant than speed.
- c. Reachability/accessibility, e.g. corresponding website functionality, ease of contact with the USN, etc.
- d. Transparency/expectation management: clearly stating which are the current limitations of the portal, i.e. with respect to available content, information on search and result rating processes, explainable delays at different levels of interactions (e.g., from interactive search delays to slow USN responses)
- e. User happiness: perceived ease of use, satisfaction

4. Methods of evaluation

A variety of methods will be used to evaluate the support quality of the OS4A in accordance with the abovementioned criteria. This includes methods from Jacobsen (2017).

(1) Automatic tracking of website use:

- a. Quantitative measures of engagement that can be derived from the use of the portal website via user tracking. There are several tools which can be used to achieve this, and tracked quantities might include (in this case tracked by the tool “matomo” (<https://matomo.org/>)): number of visits, number of unique visitors, the temporal dynamics of both, location of the visitors, actions of the visitors (page views, downloads, outlinks, ...), percentage of visitors that bounced (left the website after one page), ...

(2) Direct user feedback on website

- a. Feedback button (like/dislike)
- b. Feedback form

(3) Analyse USN requests:

- a. Log from which part of OS4A USN is called
- b. How many users’ searches have as an endpoint the USN/number of USN requests

(4) User experience tests with different users

- a. User feedback group: this group will be established as a continuous feedback mechanism to test individual features, designs, etc.
- b. Hands-on workshops to test OS4A functionalities and features, e.g., at conferences
- c. Use of the Usability Lab at HAW-Hamburg

5. Summary and Outlook

The OneStop4All (OS4A) acts as the access point to all resources of the NFDI4Earth, such as articles, learning materials, tools and software, repositories and archives, web services and other infrastructures and services. The OS4A obtains metadata of all content via the KnowledgeHub and thus makes the content relevant to the user findable. Thus, the user-friendliness and quality of the content is crucial for the success of NFDI4Earth.

The portal should support the users as best as possible in their concerns. How good the quality of this support is for the user can be divided into the user-friendliness of the portal, the quality of the content presented, the technical breadth of the content and resources, and ultimately the support for the user.

This document describes the preliminary work that was done to derive criteria. Additionally, it was shown how a scheme for evaluation can be defined and finally which methods are necessary for the evaluation.

The criteria, categories and methods presented here are initially formulated vaguely, as they were developed during the conception phase of the various components of NFDI4Earth. We are thus aware that these criteria and methods will have to be elaborated in detail and constantly developed further after the initial implementation phase and on the basis of feedback from the community.

References

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A. Results of the brainstorming meeting in MIRO

Last meeting expert group "User", autumn 2022.

Participants in each product group have considered how and by which methods their product, but also other products, could be evaluated. The colours indicate which product the corresponding methods refer to. These considerations formed the basis of this deliverable.

Figure 1: Screenshot of Miro board

Figure 2: Screenshot of Miro board